

PROCESSES IN INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS AND THEIR IMPACT ON ATTITUDES**Salamova A.***Teacher of the Department of General Sciences of ADPU Sheki branch***Abstract**

We all interact with other people to a greater or lesser extent in our daily lives and experience different levels of interpersonal relationships. Building relationships is one of the most basic characteristics of people and a reflection of their interaction with the social environment. Therefore, interpersonal relationships are a widely studied area of social psychology.

As a social being, humans must form relationships with other individuals to satisfy their many needs. The quality of established relationships has a significant impact on an individual's life. It can be said that many of the problems that people face throughout their lives are related to the relationships that they make with other individuals in one way or another. For this reason, it is of great importance for people to establish a healthy relationship with the people around them, to successfully overcome the problems they face, and to achieve satisfaction with life.

Keywords: relationship, attachment, empathy, conflict, loneliness.

Main text of the article. Establishing relationships is one of the most important needs in humans, as it is in many living things. A human baby is in a socialization process from birth, and this socialization is based on mutual relationships. The relationship that a newborn establishes with its mother and caregiver expands with peer and friend relationships, institutional relationships, and adult emotional relationships in the following years, and the human being becomes part of a wide network of relationships. The mutual relationship established with parents includes characters such as friends, spouses, teachers, and coworkers during the development process.

Socialization - there are also damaging relationships. Socialization is the process of learning to be a part of society, to exist in society, and to internalize the norms and values of society from the moment a person is born, through institutions such as family, friendship, religion, school, and the state.

Humans are the subjects of interpersonal and intergroup relationships. Although there are some preferred forms of loneliness, humans need to establish mutual relationships. Unpreferred loneliness is difficult and often creates negative effects on humans, especially mentally. According to studies, most people are happy to make friends and establish close relationships, and the opposite situation leads to unhappy and negative emotional states.

In a study conducted on how people give meaning to their lives, 89% of the participants responded to the question of what gives meaning to their lives by stating that it is the interpersonal relationships they establish. In this sense, the relationship a person establishes with their environment and the satisfaction of this relationship are very important.

Interpersonal relationships, which cover a large part of our daily lives, have three fundamental aspects. These are: interdependence, the need for completion, and emotional attachment. No person is isolated, and no relationship is isolated; they all take place within a social context. When we consider any relationship we are in, we see that it is not just a process of dependence, completion, and commitment between two people, but also a part of a large network of relationships that are a

combination of other relationships. Interpersonal relationships have a holistic quality. Interpersonal relationships are more than isolated moments of interaction. Therefore, we are faced not only with a relationship alone, but with a network of relationships. Relationships are determined by the people who establish the relationship, but also by the context in which the relationship is established. However, interpersonal relationships are not only positive relationships. There are also relationships that are harmful to the parties, negative, and that damage emotional integrity.

“Human beings establish interpersonal relationships throughout their lives, and these relationships grow, develop, dissolve and end. While living a relationship, people go through some important processes. The processes include attachment, *conflict, empathy and loneliness*” [1, p.121-125].

Attachment, it is the situation where the baby responds positively to his/her parents or the caregiver who meets his/her needs and takes care of him/her, feels the need for them in case of fear and feels safe with them. However, attachment is not only related to infancy, it lasts throughout life, but the attachment established in infancy is very important in the development of a sense of trust. Attachment has two functions: creating a sense of security and learning about the environment. When babies are afraid, they turn to the people they are attached to in order to overcome this fear and expect a supportive response from them. At the same time, the reactions of the person they are attached to determine what the babies will think about the environment. When the baby or child encounters a new situation and does not know how to react, they turn to the people they are attached to and follow their reactions. Babies tend to show similar reactions to the parents or caregiver. If the person they are attached to is afraid of the new situation, the baby will understand that it is something to be afraid of, and if they react positively, they will react positively.

How babies experience the attachment process is one of the determinants of the interpersonal relationships they will experience in the future.

There are three types of attachment in babies: secure attachment, anxious attachment, and avoidant attachment.

Secure connection, occurs when the parent or caregiver is sensitive to the baby's needs, meets their needs and establishes a positive interaction with the baby. These babies trust the person they depend on, do not worry, do not fear abandonment and see themselves as valuable.

Anxious attachment, occurs when the parent or caregiver does not respond consistently to the baby's needs. Sometimes the need is met and sometimes indifferent. This affects the baby. Since the baby cannot predict how the caregiver will respond to his needs, attachment becomes anxious. He tends to stay close to the caregiver and feel insecure even in their presence. He shows nervousness and anxiety.

Avoidant attachment, occurs when the parent or caregiver is indifferent to the baby's needs, rejects the baby's attempts at closeness, or is rejecting. There is little difference to the baby between a caregiver and a stranger, and neither is reassuring to him.

The effects of these attachment types, which are formed as a result of how much the baby's needs are met, do not remain only in infancy. The form of interpersonal relationships established in adulthood is also determined by how these needs are met. Babies who have experienced a secure attachment process with their parents or caregivers establish satisfying and long-term relationships in adulthood. They do not experience anxiety about abandonment, and they open up to the other person easily. Their self-confidence and self-esteem are high. Babies who have formed avoidant attachments with their parents or caregivers trust others less in adulthood, have trust issues, and have difficulty establishing close relationships. They are cautious when establishing interpersonal relationships, are emotionally distant, and do not trust others. Since they have problems with trust, they are less likely to be satisfied in their relationships. They have a low tendency to establish romantic relationships. Babies who have anxious attachments with their parents or caregivers are anxious in their relationships as adults. They want to be close to the person they establish a relationship with, but they worry about whether they will be reciprocated. They have many emotional ups and downs, tending towards romantic feelings such as love at first sight, but their anxiety levels are always high.

Conflict, it is one of the processes that occur frequently in interpersonal relationships. It occurs frequently not only in interpersonal relationships but also between individuals and groups or groups and groups. It can be seen in business life, at home, in friendships and even between states. Conflict can be damaging, but it can also lead the relationship in a new direction and be repairing. It can include destructive behaviors, but it can also create a compromise reached as a result of discussion between the parties to the relationship.

There is no relationship that progresses without conflict. Conflicts occur between the parties to a greater or lesser extent. Conflict is a process that occurs when the behaviors of one person interfere with those of the

other. Conflict usually occurs when the goals of the parties to the relationship are incompatible.

The sources of conflict can be roughly divided into three groups:

Certain behaviors: Some conflicts are caused by behaviors of one of the parties. For example, if your roommate throws a party at your house on a day when you should be studying for an exam, you will be disturbed. You will be blocked on the way to your goal.

Norms: The source of some conflicts is people ignoring the norms they must follow and the roles they must fulfill. For example, if your roommate doesn't clean even though it's your turn, this will create conflict in your relationship because they haven't done their share of the task.

Personal tendencies: The source of some conflicts is the personality structures of the parties. Conflict may arise because your roommate is a messy person. Conflict often occurs when the relationship is not satisfying. The satisfaction of the parties in the relationship is decisive for the relationship to continue. So how do people react to this situation when their relationships are not satisfying? According to the model developed by Rusbult and Zembrodt regarding relationship dissatisfaction, there are four main reactions to experiencing dissatisfaction in the relationship, and these responses differ in two dimensions. These dimensions are active or passive and constructive or destructive. The reactions are expression, commitment, ignoring and abandonment.

Expression: Expression is an active and constructive response. It involves discussing the problems that caused the conflict, suggesting compromises, working for the relationship, trying to change oneself or the other party, or both parties.

Showing commitment: It is a passive and constructive response. The person is passive but has an optimistic supportive response that things will improve. It includes decisions such as "I will give it some time" or "I will try to forgive and forget."

Don't ignore: It is a passive and destructive response. He/she refuses to deal with the problem and allows the situation to get worse because he/she does not make an effort. The ignoring response includes ignoring the parties in the relationship, spending less time with them, criticizing them, abusing them physically and/or emotionally, and being unfaithful.

Abandonment: An active and destructive response, abandonment involves leaving the relationship completely. The abandonment response may include ending a relationship, such as a formal divorce in a married couple, leaving home in a roommate relationship, or resigning from a job with which one is in conflict.

Constructive and destructive dimensions indicate the effect of the reaction on the relationship. While ignoring and abandoning tend to destroy the relationship, expressing and committing aim to maintain the relationship. There are three determinants of which of these reactions will be shown. These are: the satisfaction the individual experiences in the relationship before the relationship enters a regression process, the investment the individual makes in the relationship, and whether

the individual has another relationship possibility as an alternative to the existing relationship.

The more satisfying the relationship was before the conflict, the more likely it is that people will respond to the conflict with expression or commitment. These constructive responses are the ones most likely to restore the relationship to its previous state. Constructive responses are also used by people who have invested a lot in the relationship because they stand to lose, and pay a high price, if the conflict ends badly. Investments include external elements such as shared resources and mutual friends, and internal elements such as self-expression or emotional investment. In terms of alternatives, there is some research that shows that good alternatives increase the likelihood of abandonment, while poor alternatives increase the likelihood of commitment.

Expression and commitment aim to maintain the relationship, while ignoring and abandonment tend to destroy it.

Communication conflicts. Communication conflicts also constitute an important dimension in interpersonal relationships. Communication has an important place in healthy relationships. Communication is basically the process of transferring messages between the source and the receiver. If there is a problem in the interaction of the two parties, a communication conflict occurs.

There are eight basic types of communication conflicts. These include:

Active conflict: it occurs when the parties to the communication are completely opposite to each other. The parties try to convince each other without listening to each other.

Passive conflict: there is a conflict between the parties, but they are passive. They resent each other and do not communicate with each other.

Existential conflict: it occurs when a person thinks that there is only one side in communication. The person's attention is not focused on the other person, but on himself. What is important is not whether the other person understands, but what he says. His message does not reach its destination, and he experiences existential conflict because he cannot communicate.

Total rejection: the person is closed to messages directed to him/her, rejects all criticism and always wants to be the leading role. No matter what the other person says, the person is closed to communication.

Prejudiced conflict: the parties have prejudices and these prejudices do not change during the discussion process. Their prejudices are so strong that they are closed to all statements of the other side.

Intensity conflict: it occurs when there is a partial agreement between the views of two people. If one party in a romantic relationship says they love each other madly, but the other party's feelings are not that intense, a conflict of intensity occurs.

Partial perception conflict: if one of the parties to the communication receives the message incompletely or partially, a partial perception conflict will occur.

Detention conflict: in this type of conflict, the message is received properly, but it is partially transmitted to the third party, not fully transmitted, or the message is modified during the transmission process.

The resolution of conflict is important for the continuity and healthy conduct of relationships. Sometimes conflict is tried to be resolved by using power and authority. Forcing causes the powerful to put pressure on the weak. Another solution is to emphasize common denominators and reduce differences to unimportant dimensions and soften the parties. Sometimes the conflict is ignored, that is, the conflict is avoided. In this way, the conflict is tried to be resolved without external intervention. It is often preferred for conflicting individuals to come together and discuss the issue, but there is not always an environment suitable for such a solution. Constructive solutions include the conflicting parties exhibiting a more flexible attitude and compromising their thoughts, in other words, finding a middle ground. Bargaining can be done between the parties for the purpose of conflict resolution. Indeed, individuals actively listening to each other and trying to understand each other can prevent conflict from arising. A competitive solution based on a win-or-lose approach prevents a positive result. Taking an accusatory attitude in conflict both causes the main issue to be distanced and takes the problem to an unmanageable level.

"The ideal process for conflict resolution is:

- ✓ creating a suitable environment,
- ✓ clarification of perceptions,
- ✓ highlighting common points,
- ✓ developing a positive outlook,
- ✓ clarification of the problem,
- ✓ determining appropriate solution options for the problem,

✓ is to make an agreement that will lead both parties to compromise" [2, p.208].

The conflict resolution process will be successful when it is carried out through healthy communication in an environment where individuals do not blame or belittle each other.

Empathy. "Empathy is derived from the Greek word *empathia*, and etymologically, the "em" suffix means "inside, inside"; the "pathia" suffix means "feeling". The concept of empathy was first used by Theodor Lipps in 1897 as the equivalent of the German word "Einfühlung". Lipps defined *Einfühlung* as follows: "The process of a person reflecting himself onto an object in front of him, feeling himself inside it, and thus understanding that object by taking it in." The word "Einfühlung" used for empathy in German means the ability to step into someone else's shoes. In English, the expression "being able to wear someone else's shoes" is used. [3, p.9].

Empathic communication is a type of communication that can eliminate these difficulties experienced in interpersonal relationships and ensure that communication occurs completely and completely. Empathy is "the ability to put oneself in the shoes of another person and to experience events and emotions the way that person experiences them" [4, p.350].

There are three important points required for establishing empathy:

- First of all, the person who will empathize must put himself in the other person's shoes and look at the world through his/her glasses. Each person's perspective on the world is different, everyone has their own unique perspective. Therefore, in order to empathize, we must look at the world through the other person's perspective.

- Secondly, we must perceive the other person's feelings and thoughts accurately.

- Finally, we must convey the empathic understanding that forms in our minds to the other person by empathizing. Empathizing and fully perceiving the other person's feelings and thoughts will cease to be a useful process if we do not convey this and do not express to them that we understand them.

The concept of empathy is sometimes confused with the concept of sympathy. Sympathy is, in its most basic sense, "suffering with someone." It is having the same feelings and thoughts that the other person has. The basis of empathy is not having the same thoughts as the other person, but understanding their feelings and thoughts.

Empathy and sympathy are two different concepts. Let's say your best friend is giving a speech in front of a large group of people. Despite being very well prepared, he stumbles and forgets what he was going to say due to anxiety and excitement. Your friend will feel embarrassed in this situation. Your embarrassment together with your friend is sympathy, while your realization that your friend is embarrassed and understanding his/her emotional state is empathy.

Loneliness. It is a very common process. Few people have probably avoided being lonely throughout their lives. In addition to its prevalence, it is also a distressing experience. Loneliness is "an unpleasant experience that occurs when a person's network of social relationships is significantly lacking, either qualitatively or quantitatively."

"The well-known psychologist R.S.Nemov characterizes loneliness from a psychological point of view and writes: A person becomes lonely when he realizes that his relationships with those people who are personally important to him are worthless, and he faces a serious lack of communication to meet his needs" [5, p.129].

The causes of loneliness are classified as changes in a person's acquired social relationships and changes in a person's desired social relationships.

Changes in acquired social relations;

Finish: the end of close emotional relationships, such as loss of a spouse or divorce.

Physical separation: it is the state of experiencing physical separation within social mobility. It includes processes such as moving to a new place, moving away from family or friends, spending long periods of time in places such as prison or hospital, and changing places for a career.

Change of status: a change in a person's position within a group or institution can cause loneliness. When your status increases, the bond between you and your peers may weaken, and you will be alone until you establish new relationships. Situations such as retirement or unemployment are also a loss of role and a cause of loneliness. Changes in desired social relationships; when a person's acquired social relationships do not match the desired social relationships, the cause of loneliness is experienced.

Developmental changes: includes age-related changes. The needs and social skills of each age are different. There may be differences between the desired social relationship and the actual social relationship before, during and after adolescence.

Situational changes: a person's desire to be with someone else is not fixed. It depends on the job, the physical environment, the person's emotional state and their likes varies.

Changes in expectations: in some cases, expectations about future social relationships can help prevent and reduce loneliness. For example, a person who is going to hospital may anticipate that their social relationships will decrease and may also lower their expectations. In some cases, expectations increase the likelihood of loneliness. A child who goes to camp may want to make many friends in a short time and may raise their expectations to unrealistic levels. When they do not make as many friends as they expect, they will experience loneliness.

Social isolation is also a situation related to a person being alone, but it cannot be used a synonym for loneliness. Loneliness is not directly related to social isolation. Social isolation is the absence of relationships with other people. Loneliness is the negative result of the cognitive evaluation of the inconsistency between current relationships and relationship standards.

Each of the processes in interpersonal relationships can affect it in different ways, depending on the type of relationship and the unique characteristics and circumstances of people.

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